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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ASSESSING AND MONITORING PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY IN MODERN EDUCATION PROCESSES

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Abstract: In the 21st century, pedagogical creativity has emerged as a critical competency within educational systems. The rapid advancement of globalization, information technologies, and the evolving needs of modern learners' demand that educators adopt innovative approaches, creative solutions, and novel teaching methods. Consequently, the assessment and monitoring of pedagogical creativity have become strategically significant issues in contemporary education.

Key words: Pedagogical creativity, teacher innovation, creative teaching, assessment criteria, monitoring systems, educational innovation, divergent thinking, Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking, little-c creativity, flow theory, student-centered learning, professional development, 360-degree feedback, digital monitoring, reflective practice.

Annotatsiya: XXI asrda pedagogik ijodkorlik ta'lim tizimlarida muhim kompetensiya sifatida shakllandi. Globallashuv, axborot texnologiyalari jadal rivojlanishi va zamonaviy o'quvchilarning o'zgarib borayotgan ehtiyojlari o'qituvchilardan innovatsion yondashuvlarni, ijodiy yechimlarni hamda yangi o'qitish usullarini qo'llashni talab qilmoqda. Shu sababli pedagogik ijodkorlikni baholash va monitoring qilish zamonaviy ta'limda strategik ahamiyatga ega masalaga aylandi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogik ijodkorlik, o'qituvchi innovatsiyasi, ijodiy ta'lim, baholash mezonlari, monitoring tizimlari, ta'limda innovatsiya, divergent tafakkur, Torrance ijodiy tafakkur testlari, kichik-c ijodkorlik, oqim nazariyasi, o'quvchi markazli ta'lim, kasbiy rivojlanish, 360 darajali fikr-mulohaza, raqamli monitoring, reflektiv amaliyot.

Аннотация: В XXI веке педагогическое творчество стало важнейшей компетенцией в системе образования. Быстрое развитие глобализации, информационных технологий и изменяющихся потребностей современных обучающихся требует от педагогов применения инновационных подходов, творческих решений и новых методов преподавания. В связи с этим оценка и мониторинг педагогического творчества приобрели стратегически важное значение в современной системе образования.

Ключевые слова: Педагогическое творчество, инновации учителя, творческое обучение, критерии оценки, системы мониторинга, образовательные инновации, дивергентное мышление, тесты Торренса на творческое мышление, "малое-с" творчество, теория потока, обучение, ориентированное на студента, профессиональное развитие, обратная связь на 360 градусов, цифровой мониторинг, рефлексивная практика.

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the 21st century, the changes taking place in the global education system have further increased the importance of pedagogical creativity. The modern educational paradigm demands that teachers not only serve as transmitters of knowledge but also act as creative leaders, innovators, and sources of inspiration. In this context, the assessment and monitoring of pedagogical creativity become particularly relevant. Pedagogical creativity refers to a teacher's ability to generate new, effective, and goal-oriented solutions within the educational process, to creatively transform traditional approaches, and to foster creativity in students. The evaluation and monitoring of this phenomenon represent a critical component of modern educational management and professional development. Due to the complexity and multidimensional nature of pedagogical creativity, the process of assessing it poses certain challenges. Therefore, it is essential to develop a scientifically grounded, comprehensive, and practically applicable system of criteria and indicators. Such a system would support the professional growth of teachers by identifying their strengths and providing clear guidance on areas for improvement. Pedagogical creativity refers to an educator's ability to address educational challenges through unconventional means, develop innovative teaching methods tailored to students' individual characteristics, and implement these approaches effectively (Beghetto & Kaufman, ^[1]). This process reflects not only the educator's creative potential but also their professional competence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Creativity and innovation have been extensively studied by prominent psychologists and educators. J. P. Guilford ^[4], in his Structure of Intellect theory, distinguished two primary types of creative thinking: convergent and divergent. Guilford emphasized that creative thinking involves the ability to solve problems in multiple ways and generate unconventional solutions. E. Paul Torrance ^[12] conducted foundational research in pedagogical creativity, developing the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking (TTCT), which remain widely used in educational practice. Torrance identified four key components of creativity: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi ^[3] introduced the Flow theory, which is applicable to pedagogical processes.

According to Csikszentmihalyi, creative activity occurs when an individual is fully immersed in a task, operating at the peak of their abilities. Ken Robinson ^[8] highlighted the role of creativity in modern education, advocating for an “educational revolution.” He argued that standardized educational approaches often suppress creativity and called for systemic changes to foster innovation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The theory of “divergent thinking” developed by Joy Paul Guilford ^[4] is one of the fundamental foundations for understanding pedagogical creativity. Guilford’s model of creativity includes four main components:

- fluency – the ability to generate a large number of ideas;
- flexibility – the ability to apply different approaches;
- originality – the ability to produce unique and novel solutions;
- elaboration – the ability to further develop and refine ideas in detail. In the pedagogical context, these components are manifested in the teacher’s processes of lesson planning, selecting teaching methods, and interacting with students.

The theory of creativity developed by Ellis Paul Torrance ^[12] is one of the most widely used foundations for assessing pedagogical creativity. Torrance’s Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking (TTCT) measure the following aspects of creativity: verbal creativity – assessing creative expression through the use of words and linguistic tools; figural creativity – assessing visual-spatial aspects of creativity; creative personality – the tendencies and orientations toward creative thinking and behavior. The Componential Model of Creativity, developed by Teresa Amabile, explains the motivational foundations of pedagogical creativity. Amabile identifies three core components of creativity:

- domain-relevant skills – knowledge and skills specific to the subject area;
- creativity-relevant processes – cognitive and personality processes that support creative thinking;
- intrinsic task motivation – internal drive to engage in a task for its own sake, out of interest or personal satisfaction.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the pedagogical context, this model highlights the importance of the teacher’s intrinsic motivation toward their professional activity, their pedagogical knowledge and skills, and the role of creative thinking processes. Anna Craft (2002) developed the concept of “little-c creativity”, which focuses on everyday creative solutions in pedagogical practice and is particularly relevant for assessing creativity in educational settings. A modern system for assessing pedagogical creativity should be based on several key criteria:

- the innovative approaches criterion, which evaluates the extent to which educators employ new teaching technologies, methods, and tools, including their ability to integrate modern technological tools, apply interactive methods, and create digital learning environments;
- the creative problem-solving criterion, which assesses an educator’s capacity to address educational challenges through non-traditional methods, make quick decisions, adopt flexible approaches, and demonstrate creativity in interactions with students;
- the student-centered approach criterion, which evaluates the educator’s ability to design teaching strategies tailored to individual student characteristics, create personalized learning plans, implement differentiated instruction, and foster inclusive educational environments;
- the active learning environment criterion, which measures the educator’s ability to create an engaging, creative learning environment that encourages student participation and fosters independent thinking, research skills, and collaborative learning opportunities;

- and the reflective practice criterion, which assesses the educator's capacity for critical self-analysis, learning from mistakes, and pursuing continuous professional development through self-improvement, professional growth, and the adoption of new experiences.

An effective system for monitoring pedagogical creativity should include observation and analysis systems involving continuous monitoring of teaching methods, interactions with students, and the ability to create a conducive learning environment, using standardized protocols and checklists during observation; portfolio methodology, which collects and analyzes the educator's creative outputs, projects, research, and professional development materials, providing evidence of progress and creative potential; a 360-degree feedback system that evaluates pedagogical creativity from multiple perspectives, including students, colleagues, administrators, and parents; and digital monitoring platforms that enable real-time tracking of performance, data collection, and analysis, providing insights into trends and supporting evidence-based decision-making.

The process of assessing pedagogical creativity includes several stages:

- the initial diagnostic stage, which identifies the educator's current level of creativity, strengths, and areas for improvement using tests, surveys, and observation;
- the goal-setting stage, in which SMART goals are established to enhance creative development; the activity planning stage, where detailed plans for training, workshops, masterclasses, and independent activities are developed;
- the implementation stage, in which the planned activities are executed with ongoing monitoring and feedback; and the final evaluation stage, where creative development is reassessed and results are analyzed to measure progress.

To enhance pedagogical creativity, several strategies are recommended, such as encouraging collaborative professional communities where educators share experiences and projects, promoting research activities through small-scale studies and dissemination of findings, establishing mentorship programs where experienced educators support younger colleagues, creating innovative projects within institutions to test new ideas and approaches, and ensuring continuous professional development through regular training, seminars, and courses. However, the assessment of pedagogical creativity may face challenges including subjectivity issues, which can be addressed by involving multiple evaluators and using standardized criteria; time and resource constraints, which can be mitigated with efficient methodologies and technological tools; lack of motivation among some educators, which can be resolved by creating an incentivized and supportive environment; and the tension between standardization and creativity, which requires careful management to maintain balance in the educational system.

CONCLUSION

The assessment and monitoring of pedagogical creativity are vital tools for improving the quality of modern education. Such a system not only supports educators' professional development but also enhances the innovative potential of the entire educational ecosystem. A successful assessment system requires evidence-based approaches, modern technologies, and active collaboration among all stakeholders. By fostering pedagogical creativity, we can significantly improve both educators' professional growth and students' learning outcomes.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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